

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

STUDYING THE SPECTRUM AND RESOLVENT OF A SECOND ORDER INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL OPERATOR ON THE ENTIRE AXIS

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Abstract. Let us consider the integro-differential equation

$$Ly \equiv -y''(x) + p(x)y'(x) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K(x, s, \rho)y'(s)ds - \lambda y(x) = f(x) \quad (2.1)$$

where $f(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}_+)$, $\mathbb{R}_+ = (-\infty, \infty)$ $\lambda = \rho^2$, $\text{Im } \rho > 0$.

Assume that $\lambda = \rho^2$, $\text{Im } \rho > 0$ is not an eigen-value of the integro-differential operator L so that the resolvent R_λ exists. We find the explicit form of the resolvent R_λ of the integro-differential operator L and show that it is a bounded integral operator.

Let $p(x)$ be a complex-valued summable function in the interval $\mathbb{R}_+$ and the kernel of the integro-differential operator (2.1) have the form:

$$K(x, s, \rho) = \begin{cases} e^{-\rho\omega_1(s-x)} P(s)K^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{for } s < x \\ e^{-\rho\omega_2(s-x)} P(s)K^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{for } s > x, \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

where ω_1, ω_2 are various roots of second degree from -1 while $K^*(x, s, \rho)$ is a complex-valued continuous bounded function on totality of (x, s, ρ) $-\infty < x, s < +\infty$, $|\text{Im } \rho| < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ variables and analytic

with respect to ρ in the domain $|\text{Im } \rho| < \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ for each fixed (x, s) , $-\infty < x, s < +\infty$.

Furthermore, let the following condition be fulfilled:

$$|P(x)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |K^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] < ce^{-2\varepsilon_0|x|}, \quad \varepsilon_0 > 0 \quad (2.3)$$

Then

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |P(x)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |K^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] dx < B_1 < \infty, \quad (2.4)$$

where B_1 is independent of ρ .

If $y(x, \lambda)$ is an eigen-function of the integro-differential operator L corresponding to the eigen-value, λ then it is determined from the equation

$$y(x, \lambda) = \frac{1}{2\rho\omega_1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} p(\tau)Q(x, \tau, \rho)y(\tau, \rho)d\tau, \quad \text{Im } \rho > 0 \quad (2.5)$$

where

$$Q(x, \tau, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1|x-\tau|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right].$$

Therefore, the eigen-values are the zeros of the Fredholm determinant

$$D(\rho) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n!} D_n(\rho) \quad (2.6)$$

We prove the following theorem.

Theorem 2.1. Let the condition (2.3) be fulfilled. Then the function $D(\rho)$ allows analytic continuation through the real positive semi-axis in the domain E , which is determined by the inequalities:

$$E = \left\{ |\rho| \geq r > 0, \operatorname{Im} \rho > \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} \right\}, \text{ where } r \text{ is a fixed number.}$$

Theorem 2.2. The set of eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L is bounded, a unique possible concentration point of the integro-differential operator L is the point $\lambda = 0$.

Theorem 3.2. If the condition (2.3) is fulfilled, then the integro-differential operator L may have only finitely many complex eigen-values.

It is proved that $|\lambda| \geq \left(\frac{B_1}{2L_0} \right)^2$ the integro-differential operator L has no eigen-values.

Keywords: integro-differential operator, theorem, condition, kernel, integral, entire axis, second order, eigen-function, values, complex-valued equation, variable, let, fixed.

Introduction.

Denote by L_0 an operator $-y''$ in $L^2(R_-^+)$.

This is a positive-definite self-adjoint operator, therefore for all $\rho = \rho_1 + \omega_1 \rho_2$ except the semi-axis $\rho_1 \geq 0$, there exists a resolvent R_λ^0 , as a bounded integral operator.

Therefore, if $f(x) \in L^2(R_-^+)$ and $\lambda = \rho^2, \operatorname{Im} \rho > 0$, then it is known that the solutions of the equations

$$-y''(x) - \rho^2 y(x) = f(x)$$

are given by the formula

$$y(x, \rho) = R_\lambda^0 f = - \int_{-\infty}^x \frac{e^{\rho \omega_1 (x-\tau)}}{2\rho \omega_1} f(\tau) d\tau - \int_x^{\infty} \frac{e^{\rho \omega_1 (\tau-x)}}{2\rho \omega_1} f(\tau) d\tau. \quad (2.7)$$

Therefore, the integro-differential equation (2.1) is equivalent to the following one:

$$y(x, \rho) = - \int_{-\infty}^x \frac{e^{\rho \omega_1 (\tau-x)}}{2\rho \omega_1} \left[f(\tau) - p(\tau) y'(\tau, \rho) - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(\tau, s, \rho) y'(s, \rho) ds \right] d\tau - \\ - \int_x^{\infty} \frac{e^{\rho \omega_1 (\tau-x)}}{2\rho \omega_1} \left[f(\tau) - p(\tau) y'(\tau, \rho) - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(\tau, s, \rho) y'(s, \rho) ds \right] d\tau.$$

Taking into account formula (2.2), we obtain

$$y(x, \rho) = - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} M_1(x, \tau, \rho) f(\tau) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} N_1(x, \tau, \rho) y'(\tau, \rho) d\tau \quad (2.8)$$

where

$$M_1(x, \tau, \rho) = \begin{cases} -\frac{e^{\rho \omega_1 (x-\tau)}}{2\rho \omega_1} & \text{for } \tau < x, \\ \frac{e^{\rho \omega_1 (\tau-x)}}{2\rho \omega_1} & \text{for } \tau > x, \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

and

$$N_1(x, \tau, \rho) = \begin{cases} \frac{e^{\rho\omega_1(x-\tau)}}{2\rho\omega_1} p(\tau) \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right] & \text{for } \tau < x, \\ \frac{e^{\rho\omega_1(x-\tau)}}{2\rho\omega_1} p(\tau) \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right] & \text{for } \tau > x. \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

Since $\lambda = \rho^2$, $\text{Im } \rho > 0$ is not an eigen-value of the integro-differential operator L , then (2.8) is solvable and we have

$$y(x, \rho) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left[M_1(x, \tau, \rho) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \Gamma_1(x, \tau, \rho) M_1(t, \tau, \rho) d\tau \right] f(\tau) d\tau = R_\lambda f, \quad (2.11)$$

where $\Gamma_1(x, \tau, \rho)$ is a solvent kernel for the kernel $N_1(x, \tau, \rho)$.

Consequently, the resolvent R_λ is an integral operator with the kernel

$$T(x, \tau, \rho) = M_1(x, \tau, \rho) + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Gamma_1(x, \tau, \rho) M_1(t, \tau, \rho) dt.$$

We now prove that this kernel in fact sets an integral operator bounded and determined in the entire space $L^2(\mathbb{R}_+)$.

At first using

$$N_1(x, \tau, \rho) = N^*(x, \tau, \rho) \text{ and } N_n^*(x, \tau, \rho) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} N^*(x, \tau, \rho) N_{n-1}^*(\tau_1, \tau, \rho) d\tau_1 \text{ we show}$$

that

$$\Gamma_1(x, \tau, \rho) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} N_n^*(x, \tau, \rho)$$

converges if $|\rho| > \frac{B}{2q}$.

For $\text{Im } \rho > 0$, we have $e^{-\rho_2|x-\tau|} \leq 1$, then from (2.10) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} |N_1^*(x, \tau, \rho)| &\leq \frac{e^{-\rho_2|x-\tau|}}{2|\rho|} |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] \leq \\ &\leq \frac{|p(\tau)|}{2|\rho|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right]; \end{aligned}$$

$$|N_2^*(x, \tau, \rho)| \leq \frac{1}{(2|\rho|)^2} |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |p(\tau_1)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] d\tau_1;$$

by induction

$$|N_n^*(x, \tau, \rho)| \leq \frac{|p(\tau)|}{(2|\rho|)^n} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \prod_{j=1}^n |p(\tau_j)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] d\tau_j.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
|\Gamma_1(x, \tau, \rho)| &\leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |N_n^*(x, \tau, \rho)| \leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{|p(\tau)|}{(2|\rho|)^n} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \prod_{j=1}^{n-1} |p(\tau_j)| \times \\
&\times \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau_j, \rho)| ds \right] d\tau_j \leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{B^{n-1}}{(2|\rho|)^n} |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] = \\
&= \frac{|p(\tau)|}{(2|\rho|)^n} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{B^{n-1}}{(2|\rho|)^{n-1}}.
\end{aligned}$$

The series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{B}{2|\rho|} \right)^{n-1}$ converges if $\frac{B}{2|\rho|} < q < 1$ or $|\rho| > \frac{B}{2q}$, i.e. in the domain

$$\frac{1}{2q} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |p(\tau_j)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] d\tau_j < |\rho|$$

there is no a spectrum of the integro-differential operator L . The sum of this series equals $\frac{2|\rho|}{2|\rho| - B}$.

Therefore, the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} N_n^*(x, \tau, \rho)$ is majorized by the convergent number series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{B}{2|\rho|} \right)^{n-1}$ and

so its sum $\Gamma_1(x, \tau, \rho)$ will be analytic with respect to ρ in the domain $\text{Im } \rho > 0$ for each fixed x . Then

the term by term differentiation of the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} N_n^*(x, \tau, \rho)$ is admissible.

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
\left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} T(x, \tau, \rho) f(\tau) d\tau \right|^2 &\leq \int \frac{e^{-\rho_2|x-\tau|}}{2|\rho|} |f(\tau) d\tau| + \frac{2|\rho|}{2|\rho| - B} |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] \times \\
&\times \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-\rho_2|x-\tau|}}{2|\rho|} |f(\tau) dt| \right\} d\tau.
\end{aligned}$$

Applying the Bunyakovsky inequality, it is easy to be convinced that

$$\left(\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-\rho_2|x-\tau|}}{2|\rho|} |f(\tau) dt| \right)^2 \leq \|f\|^2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-\rho_2|x-\tau|}}{4|\rho|^2} d\tau = \frac{\|f\|^2}{4\rho_2|\rho|^2}.$$

Therefore

$$|R_\lambda f| \leq \frac{\|f\|^2}{4\rho_2|\rho|^2} \left[1 + \left| \frac{2|\rho|}{2|\rho| - B} \right|^2 B^2 \right]$$

So, for any function $f(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}_-^+)$ the formula (2.11) determines the function $y(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}_-^+)$, it is easy to verify that $y(x, \rho)$ satisfies the equation (2.8) and consequently the integro-differential equation (2.1).

So, the closed operator R_λ is defined on the entire space $L^2(\mathbb{R}_-^+)$.

Let now $y(x, \lambda)$ be an eigen function of the integro-differential operator L corresponding to the eigenvalue λ .

Then it is defined from the equation

$$y(x, \lambda) = \frac{1}{2\rho\omega_1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} p(\tau) Q(x, \tau, \rho) y(\tau, \rho) d\tau, \operatorname{Im} \rho > 0, \quad (2.12)$$

where

$$Q(x, \tau, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1|x-\tau|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right].$$

Therefore, the eigen-values are the zeros of the Fredholm determinant

$$D(\rho) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n!} D_n(\rho), \quad (2.13)$$

where

$$D_n(\rho) = \frac{1}{(2\rho\omega_1)^n} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \det \|Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j)\| \prod_{k=1}^n p(\tau_k) d\tau_k, \quad i, j = \overline{1, n} \quad (2.14)$$

Here we introduce the following denotations:

$$\det \|Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j)\| = Q_\rho \begin{pmatrix} \tau_1 & \tau_2 & \dots & \tau_n \\ \tau_1 & \tau_2 & \dots & \tau_n \end{pmatrix}$$

and

$$Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j) = e^{\rho\omega_1|\tau_i-\tau_j|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau_j, \rho)| ds \right], \quad i, j = \overline{1, n}.$$

Therefore, the operator R_λ does not exist only for those ρ for which $D(\rho) = 0$.

We now prove the following theorem.

Theorem 2.1. Let the condition (2.3) be fulfilled. Then the function $D(\rho)$ allows analytic continuation through the real positive semi-axis in the domain E , which is determined by the inequalities:

$$E = \left\{ |\rho| \geq r > 0, \operatorname{Im} \rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} \right\}, \text{ where } r \text{ is a fixed number.}$$

Proof. In the domain E the quantity $Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j), i, j = \overline{1, n}$ is determined for all ρ and for the fixed values τ_i, τ_j is an analytic function of ρ .

In the domain E the following estimation is valid:

$$Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j) = e^{\rho_2|\tau_i-\tau_j|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau_j, \rho)| ds \right] \leq e^{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}(|\tau_i|+|\tau_j|)} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right]. \quad (2.15)$$

In what follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \det \|Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j)\| \prod_{j=1}^n p(\tau_j) &= \det \|Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j)\| \prod_{i=1}^n p(\tau_j) e^{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n |\tau_j|} e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} |\tau_j|} = \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^n p(\tau_j) e^{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n |\tau_j|} \det \|Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j) e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} |\tau_j|}\|. \end{aligned}$$

In the domain E by virtue of the estimation (2.15) we obtain :

$$\left| Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j) e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} |\tau_j|} \right| = e^{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} |\tau_i|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau_j, \rho)| ds \right].$$

Applying the Hadamard inequality, we obtain:

$$\left| \det \left\| Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j) e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} |\tau_j|} \right\| \right| \leq n^2 \prod_{j=1}^n e^{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} |\tau_j|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau_j, \rho)| ds \right]$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \det \left\| Q_\rho(\tau_i, \tau_j) \right\| \prod_{j=1}^n |p(\tau_j)| \right| &\leq n^2 \prod_{j=1}^n |p(\tau_j)| e^{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} |\tau_j|} e^{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n |\tau_j|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau_j, \rho)| ds \right] = \\ &= n^2 \prod_{j=1}^n |p(\tau_j)| e^{\varepsilon_0 |\tau_j|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau_j, \rho)| ds \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

Using the conditions (2.3) and (2.16) , we obtain:

$$|D_n(\rho)| \leq \frac{n^2}{(2r)^n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \cdots \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \prod_{j=1}^n |p(\tau_j)| e^{2\varepsilon_0 |\tau_j|} \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau_j, \rho)| ds \right] d\tau \leq \left(\frac{\sqrt{n} B_1}{2r} \right)^n$$

for all $\rho \in E$.

$$\text{Therefore, in the domain } E, |D_n(\rho)| \leq 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\frac{\sqrt{n} B_1}{2r} \right)^n.$$

By the D'Alambert test, a number series converges, therefore the series of analytic in the domain E functions $D_n(\rho)$ converges uniformly, i.e. $D(\rho)$ is a function analytic in the domain E . Theorem 2.1. proved.

Let us consider the function of L

$$f(L) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(\sqrt{n}L)^n}{n!}, (L \geq 0).$$

$f(L)$ is determined for all $L \geq 0$ and monotonically increases in this domain

$f(0) = 0$, therefore, there exists a unique L_0 determined by the condition

$$f(L_0) = 1.$$

Now, we choose such a number r that $\frac{B_1}{2r} < L_0$, i.e. for

$$r > \frac{B_1}{2L_0} = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{2\varepsilon|x|} |p|(x) \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] dx}{2L_0} \quad (2.17)$$

Then for

$$|\rho| \geq r > \frac{B_0}{2L_0},$$

$$|D(\rho)| \geq 1 - \left| \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\sqrt{n} B_1}{2r} \right)^n \frac{1}{n!} \right| \neq 0$$

the i.e. for rather large $|\rho|$ $D(\rho) \neq 0$.

So, $D(\rho) \neq 0$ for rather large $|\rho|$ in the domain E . Therefore, it follows from the Fredholm theory that complex-valued values of the integro-differential operator L form at most a denumerable set of points with a unique possible concentration point in zero .

Theorem 2.2. The set of eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L is bounded, a unique possible concentration point of the integro-differential operator L is the point $\lambda = 0$.

The formula (2.17) estimates also the radius of the circle in the complex λ plane ($\lambda = \rho^2$), outside of which there are knowingly no eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L . More exactly for $|\lambda| \geq R$,

where $R = \left(\frac{B_1}{2L_0}\right)^2$ the integro-differential operator L has no eigen values.

Show that $\lambda = 0$ is not a concentration point of eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L if condition (2.3) is fulfilled.

Indeed, according to theorem 2.1 in this case the function $D(\rho)$ will be analytic on the entire real axis: therefore, the zeros of the function $D(\rho)$ can not have limiting points on the real axis.

Theorem 2.3. The point $\lambda = 0$ is not an eigen-value of the integro-differential operator L if the condition (2.3) is fulfilled.

Proof. For $\rho = 0$ the integro-differential equation

$$y''(x) + \rho^2 y(x) = p(x)y'(x) + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(x, s, \rho)y'(s)ds \quad (2.18)$$

and condition (2.2) takes the form

$$-y''(x) + p(x)y'(x) + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(x, s)y'(s)ds = 0 \quad (2.19)$$

$$K(x, s) = \rho(s)K^*(x, s), \quad (2.20)$$

where $K(x, s, 0) = K(x, s)$ and $K^*(x, s, 0) = K^*(x, s)$.

To prove the theorem, it suffices to show that the integro-differential equation (2.19) has no solutions belonging to $L^2(\mathbb{R}_+)$.

Consider the integral equation for $x \geq 0$:

$$y_k(x) = X^{k-1} + \int_x^{\infty} \left[(\tau - x)p(\tau)y'_k(\tau) + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (s - x)K(\tau, s)y'_k(s)ds \right] d\tau, k = 1, 2 \quad (2.21)$$

Taking into account the condition (2.20), we obtain:

$$y_k(x) = x^{k-1}Hy'_k, k = 1, 2, \quad (2.22)$$

where

$$Hy'_k = \int_x^{\infty} (\tau - x)p(\tau) \left[1 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |K^*(s, \tau)| ds \right] y'_k(\tau) d\tau.$$

Show that each of these equations have solutions that as $x \rightarrow \infty$ have the following asymptotics:

$$y_k(x) = x^{k-1} + O(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}), k = 1, 2. \quad (2.23)$$

Now we provide a proof for $y_1(x)$.

We write the solution of the equation (2.22) in the form of the Neumann series

$$y_1(x) = 1 + H1 + H^2 1 + \dots \quad (2.24)$$

Repeating the arguments of theorem 1.1 [4], we can easily show by induction that

$$|H^n 1| \leq \frac{ce^{-2n\varepsilon_0 x}}{2(2n)!!\varepsilon_0^{n+2}}.$$

Therefore, the series (2.24) converges uniformly for $x \geq 0$, and $|y_1^2(x)| \leq A_1$ for $x \in \mathbb{R}^+ = (0, \infty)$.

We now estimate the integral terms and in (2.22) for $k = 1$

$$|Hy_1'| \leq A_1 |H1| \leq \frac{A_1 c e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}}{(2\varepsilon_0)^2} \rightarrow O(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x})$$

as $x \rightarrow +\infty$.

By the same taken, the relation (2.22) is proved for $k = 1$.

It is clear that $y_1(x)$ will be the solution of the integro-differential equation (2.19) for $x \geq 0$.

In that follows, $y_1(x)$ does not belong to $L^2(\mathbb{R}_-^+)$.

We continue $y_1(x)$ for $x \leq 0$ as a solution for the integro-differential equation (2.19)

After substituting $y_1(x) = xu(x)$, we carry out analytic construction for $y_2(x)$.

It is seen from (2.23) that $y_1(x), y_2(x)$ are linearly independent. Therefore, since all $y_k(x) \notin L^2(\mathbb{R}_-^+), k = 1, 2$, then any solution of (2.18) is $\notin L^2(\mathbb{R}_-^+)$ as well.

The theorem is proved.

Summarizing, we can formulate the following main theorem.

Theorem 2.4. If the condition (2.3) is fulfilled, then the integro-differential operator L may have only finitely many complex eigen-values.

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